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A CALL FOR BROADER ETHICAL PERSPECTIVES WHEN ARCHITECTS ENGAGE IN CLIMATE RESILIENT DESIGN

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Abstract

The European Union's ambitious targets for decarbonising its building stock by 2050 confront the architecture profession with a moral imperative that poses significant challenges in responding to the climate crisis. Within architectural practice climate resilient design strategies offer a plethora of opportunities to engage and respond to these issues. Sustainable renovation strategies, such as Deep Renovation (DR), have emerged as vital tools in mitigating the environmental impact of existing buildings. However, given the advantages of these methods there is still a considerable gap in understanding the ethical obligations associated with this work. This article tracks existing discourse surrounding sustainable renovation strategies and the intersection between ethics, professional practice and care theory. The article identifies limitations surrounding current codes of practice, highlighting how current ethical frameworks aim to prioritise profitability, risk management and personal interest over broader social, ecological and political considerations. The discussion argues that the implementation of care theory, guided by feminist discourse surrounding critical care, can enhance ethical considerations architects consider when implementing strategies to mitigate the climate crisis. Moreover, the article aims to champion the significance of collective identity, stewardship and accountability in encouraging new modes of practice within industry, whilst contributing to current scholarly discourse.

Keywords: ethics, deep renovation, care theory.

1. POSITIONALITY STATEMENT

As an architectural designer and Woman of Colour (WoC) I have personal interest in advocating for the inclusion of alternative perspectives in architectural practice and ethics. Both my professional and ethnographic background influence how I make sense of the data presented here, however careful attention has been taken to acknowledge and manage the risk of biased assumptions which can present themselves. A reflective positionality is one strategy which has been utilised in the preparation of this article.

2. INTRODUCTION

In this article I explore the evolving discourse surrounding sustainable renovation practices within architectural practice, in response to climate neutrality goals outlined by the European Union (EU). These

efforts aim to improve the energy efficiency of existing building stock whilst charting a way forward for the building industry to decarbonise. Although the path to reaching this goal has proven challenging, sustainable renovation methods, namely Deep Renovation (DR) defined as, “renovation methods which include the, “full economic energy efficiency potential of improvement works [...] of existing buildings” (Shnapp, S., Sitha, R., & Laustsen, J. 2013). I explore the intersection between these renovation strategies, ethics and professional practice to expose deficiencies existing in current modes of practice, in architecture’s response to the climate crisis. I argue that there is a need for broader ethical considerations by incorporating elements of care theory and feminist discourse to move beyond current limitations which prioritise self interest, professional codes and compliance in the fulfilment of projects. Ultimately, these deficiencies demonstrate that a research gap exists in studying the relationship of care theory and ethics in our response to the wicked problems of the climate crisis within our industry. Therefore, I propose that ethical practice within the landscape of decarbonisation efforts should champion the collective responsibility of the profession to the Earth, ecology and humanity.

3. SCHOLARLY PERSPECTIVES OF RENOVATION AND BROADER INTERACTIONS

Current scholarly debate indicates a pluralistic evolution of our understanding of what renovation is and what its ecological and socio-political intra-connections are. A recent approach applies methods of co-creating to renovation projects by prioritising citizen engagement, design activism and material discourse. This approach is facilitated through co-operative organisations and is referred to as Citizen Led Renovation (CDR). This bottom-down approach to sustainable renovation allows architects to facilitate design activism and agency and is observed in the case studies of organisations like Ecovision in Ireland and Izgrei in Bulgaria that aim to promote the deployment of community-led renovation initiatives. Despite the growing uptake of these programs there is a need to examine the relationship between these emerging practices and the ethical obligation of the architects who enable it.

The book *Material Reform: Building For a Post Carbon Future* (2022) by research collective Material Cultures collates a number of essays discussing the role of systems, cultures and infrastructures that shape architectural industry and the destructive ecologies it contributes to. The collective of authors critically present arguments which advocate for a holistic approach to how architects can deal with the existing urban fabric. Although the book does not specifically mention renovation activities, the arguments presented by the group of authors encourage debate surrounding our relationship to existing practices within architectural practice by questioning the foundations of architectural historical theory, practice, and material culture and their intersections. Alongside these diverse perspectives Cook (2020) presents an interesting argument in understanding renovation as a material future-making practice which can shape broader cultural values and histories which elicit an ontological perspective of renovation methodologies. Cook acknowledges the vast scholarly literature available on renovation in terms of energy efficiency, health, and design but little exists concerning the meaning and experience of renovating and the way it is practised in society. Her argument is that renovation is much more than a metric-based remodelling process but instead a discursive practice based on materiality that shapes and envisions futures. Cook’s argumentation is important because it brings into question how architects who lead renovation activities may be responsible for the anticipated futures of users who are yet to occupy a space and what type of ethical responsibilities this may entail. Furthermore, Cook (2020) stresses the relationship between an embodied and material-centric approach to buildings, further strengthening the case for a holistic perspective on renovation practices if we are to take Clapham’s cues and acknowledge renovation as an embodied future-making practice. Botta (2005) adds to scholarly debate surrounding alternative understandings of sustainable renovation with the inclusion of “careful renovation” and “environmentally-friendly renovation.” Botta defines these terms as, “careful renovation is that of preserving the character of the building as well as its values as they are perceived by its user...and environmentally-friendly renovation as, “renovation actions that pay special attention to energy efficiency, water conservation and the use of renewable materials...to preserving natural resources and avoiding environmental pollution.” (Botta 2005, pg14) Although Botta finds fruitful ground in these theoretical

arguments she goes beyond the individual experience to argue that prioritising collective meaning allows architects to understand a place in such a way that allows for intervention “without destroying existing values.” (Botta 2005, pg18) This is a very useful perspective in my line of argumentation because it reinforces the notion that renovation has broader, more widespread interactions as it is a collective practice which informs and shapes present and future realities. Additionally, renovation therefore has the power to inform both our present and future relationship with the planet and the complex actor networks it simultaneously encapsulates and generates.

4. ETHICS, SUSTAINABILITY AND THE ASSOCIATED CHALLENGES FOR ARCHITECTS

Sadri (2012) argues that the professional codes generated by organisations often protect the individual responsibility of architects and ignore the collective responsibility of the profession. Additionally, Sadri critiques professional ethics by examining the “transformation of discipline into a profession” and the disregard for architects ethical responsibility to humanity. Sadri’s discussion denotes the links between power, authority, capital, and professional ethics, noting that the accumulation of such cultural factors is cause for concern in the profession. He argues that, “Architectural ethics which are built on universal human achievements and values...shall approach architecture in a holistic manner, as a cultural and social phenomenon...” by looking at “the bigger picture” as he suggests will focus more on humanity, supersede boundaries reinforced by professionalism and include multi-actor networks. Most importantly, Sadri argues for a boundless perspective which goes beyond the traditional profession conduct documents our architectural practice relies on to move towards a collective responsibility. Although these arguments are limited to comments on the professional practice code of conduct outlined by the Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA), I believe they do find applicability in commenting on the ethical responsibility of the profession as a whole. Sadri’s argumentation successfully alludes to the historical inability of our profession and its existing ethical framework to capture a responsibility to humanity and the planet. Furthermore, his discussion touches on the inflexibility of architecture as a profession in proposing new ways of being and dealing with the world. Fuller Jong & Mellersh-Lucas (2007) examine the ethics of sustainable housing design and the dilemma it presents for practising architects. Their research focuses on the concept of sustainability and the global issue to understand what it is. The relationship between sustainability and ethics is brought into question here by discussing how architects respond to choice or the “ultimate choice” which is the “antithesis of self-interest as it is in the interest of others. These ‘others’ include future generations, the poor in developing countries, living and non-human species.” (Fuller et al., 2007 pg 233) This aspect of their study is particularly useful in perceiving sustainability within renovation, in particular the perspective this review takes by situating sustainable renovation as an activity that impacts present and future others.

5. CHALLENGES OF CURRENT SUSTAINABLE RENOVATION PRACTICES AND THEORY

Passoni, Marini, Belleri, & Menna (2020) define the term Sustainable Renovation (SBR) as, “renovation of existing buildings is commonly intended as the upgrade of constructions by implementing green technologies and eco-friendly materials” which leans on definitions of Sustainable Development first established in 1987 at the Brundtland Commission (General Assembly of the United Nations). More recently, Jensen, Thuvander, Femenias, & Visscher, (2022) note that SBR implementation is rapidly developing to meet the needs of ageing building stock globally and notes in their study that the drivers are well studied, mainly a result of economic and informational aspects in particular the relationship management between stakeholders during long term staged renovation becomes an important aspect. They suggest a research gap exists in studying the diversity of new strategies of renovation Fawsett (2014). The findings of Jensen Thuvander Femenias & Visscher (2022) are illuminating in that they highlight gaps in the field where alternative methodologies and practices of renovation can exist. Although they speak about the relational dynamic that must be managed between stakeholders, primarily between the tenant and occupant, there is little mention of the relationship

between occupants, tenant and other network actors, primarily non-human elements such as the local ecology, histories, and material agents. The outcome of their research paper demonstrates that it seems challenging for researchers to bridge between scientific and thematic discourse when considering renovation. Further, this knowledge gap highlights how the application of theoretical perspectives, especially in critical care theory, may propose a useful approach to the issue. Additionally, Kamari, Jensen, Corrao, & Kirkegaard (2019) reviewed barriers of renovation to reveal a lack of methodologies in proposing a holistic multi-methodology for sustainable renovation. Their study provides a framework to improve group learning and group decision making to make the renovation process efficient. They argue that cultural and transformational changes impact the broader community beyond the building occupants and address the “complex social interdependencies” involved in renovation projects. (Kamari et al., 2019 Pg52) Although this study successfully demonstrates how new methodologies in renovation can indeed have holistic benefits, they fail to address the ethical obligations of the architect in this process, particularly those which go beyond legal and professional obligations.

6. OPPORTUNITIES OF CARING REFORM IN BROADENING ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

In the book *Critical Care: Architecture and Urbanism for a Broken Planet* cultural theorist and writer Elke Krasny sees caring architecture as much more than the building and construction of care facilities, but rather an approach to rethinking critical care through the lens of architecture and urbanism as a remedy to the “broken and damaged” state of our planet (McFarlane & Ricci, 2019). Krasny’s relationship to care as she intimates is closely aligned with Critical Theory first established in the 1930s at the Frankfurt School in Germany. Krasny stems her theoretical exploration in the work of political theorists Joan Toronto in *Moral Boundaries: A Political Boundary Argument for an Ethic of Care* (1993) and Bernice Fischer who elaborate on the definition of care in architecture as, “...a species activity that includes everything we do to maintain, continue and repair our ‘world’...all of which we seek to include in a complex life-sustaining web.” Krasny’s conversations about care discourse in architecture theory deals with why the profession has been hesitant to find usefulness in care theory, as she speaks about its connection to the feminization of the career and overriding patriarchal histories of the architect as a solitary, male figure. Although Krasny et al. allude to the relationship between power, labour, and architecture the case studies presented in the book encourage us to see how elements of care theory can be applied to architectural practice. Moreover, these examples are important in developing the discussion surrounding the ethical considerations of architects and provide a precedent for how we can begin to associate care and sustainable renovation.

However, these forms of social intervention are not without contestation, and although I believe there are still many positive opportunities in the implementation of caring principles in regards to ethical considerations of sustainable renovation, they are important to note. Card (2011) introduces a critical perspective of democratic social architecture in relation to socio-economics, and his discussion is useful in shaping the ethical obligation of architects during renovation. Card details his initial inspiration was drawn from Sergio Palleroni’s book *Green for All* in which he defines, “the responsibility of an architect to be inclusive, to include all things about this world, and that means all communities.” Card goes on to also note the significance of Bruno Lator’s actor network theory discussion in *Reassembling the Social* (2005) where inquiries should be instigated from controversies. The controversies Card speaks of is the imperialistic tendency of social architecture, with the only remedy to its imposition on local communities he suggests is democratically accounting for, including and document vast network actors within local communities, or that, “real equality they need to root their practices in local interactions, social movements, and new democratic processes of environmental production.” (Card, pg 230) This is a crucial aspect to consider in ethical renovation practices, particularly those informed by feminist theory because it illuminates the need for relational dynamics to be taken into account during complex and invasive processes like renovation.

7. FUTURE IMPLICATIONS

By extension, these theories beg the question: How can we as architects begin to take into account the multiplicity of perspectives, histories and futures of both human and non-human elements during renovation projects? Although this review demonstrates the challenges in approaching renovation through this lens, what Card does successfully in fact demonstrate is what we should not seek to do, that is give in to existing power dynamics present in border socio-political and production spheres, and that continue to inform how we work. Therefore the development of these holistic frameworks used to enhance renovation work can be defined as social and as democratic but in a way that speaks to, rather than speaks for actors within a network. I believe the incorporation of care theory into architectural practice, namely renovation projects presents an opportunity to deal with these challenges and questions. These methods incorporate material culture, agency, and caring into wider decarbonization efforts, drawing intra-connections and encouraging the adoption of holistic frameworks in sustainable renovation that prioritise care and collaboration. These dynamics can still allow for client and community project deliverables to be met, whilst simultaneously instigating change in our profession by reforming ethical practices which are not based on solely managing risk and reputation during renovation. These approaches promote a shift towards more inclusive, responsible, and environmentally responsive architectural practice, whilst ensuring a commitment to needs greater than industry and profitability are met, and as noted in the scholarly arguments presented in this literature review, there is a growing need for these propositions to be investigated and tested. Although such approaches are not without criticism, the integration of care theory contributes to the debate around the implications of the type of work we facilitate as architects going beyond the professional ethical framework to encourage collaboration, stewardship, and collective identity.

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